

THE EMERGENCE OF TOPONYMS

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One place from another, one street from another, next to one street from the street, to distinguish mountains, cities and villages from each other people invented names. As place names, geographical names or toponyms. Toponyms are studied by the science of toponymy.

Toponymy comes from the Greek words *topos* - place and *onoma* (or *onima*) - name composed. Place names, that is, toponymy, are divided into several types. These are hydronomics (Greek *hydro* - water), i.e. rivers, lakes, seas, streams, canals, bays, the names of straits, waterfalls: *oronimia* (Greek *oros* - mountain), i.e. land relief forms of the surface - names of mountains, peaks, hills, valleys, plains; *oikonymy* (Greek *oikos* - house), *polynymy* (Greek *polis* - city) or *urbanonymy* (Latin *urbos* - city), that is, the names of villages and cities, *microtoponymy* (Greek *micros* - small), that is, small objects: springs, wells, fields, meadows, groves, ravines, roads, bridges and even horses names of some trees that have. In addition, the names of various peoples and clans. Toponyms named with are called *ethnotoponyms* (Greek *ethnos* - people). Person toponyms with names are *anthropotoponyms* (Greek *anthropos* - person) can be called.

Toponymy is geographical such as cities, villages, rivers, lakes, mountains while studying names, their origin, history, this science helps linguists,

It also provides rich scientific material for historians. Geographical names, that is, toponyms, are part of the vocabulary of the language subject to the laws. Of course, linguistics is the study of linguistics need. So, toponymy is a part of the science of *onomastics* that studies proper nouns and is included among the linguistic sciences.

On the other hand, geographical names as the most important element of the map reflects the characteristics of the nature of a country or people. This is the point of view. Toponymy can be included in the list of geographical sciences. At the same time, place names are closely related to the history of society. How to name places is primarily the needs of society at a certain stage is determined by, dealing with toponymy without knowing the history of place names does not give the expected result. That is why toponymy is a science of history ranks among so, toponymy is between three big fields: linguistics, geography, history is a science.

Therefore, the facts of toponymy were diverse in character correct interpretation only when linguistic, historical and geographical material is involved possible.

A toponym is also a geographical name word but toponyms are nouns. Famous nouns are relatively late in language development originated from related horses in stages. Ancient languages did not have proper nouns they say Aboriginal languages of Australia, Africa and America there are very few noble horses. Similar nouns, some word combinations in such languages acting as horses. Such phrases are increasingly stable form takes People call places in a small area known to them as "Balik Catching Lake", "Flooding Stream", "Sheep Killed Wilderness", "Pig Stream" They are called by word combinations consisting of whole sentences.

Such word combinations that represent concrete geographical objects and similar horses gradually become famous horses. Similar nouns are toponymized in this way, that is, they become toponyms.

For example, the word apple is a general concept that represents apple orchards in general will remain a kindred horse. If this concept is individualized, a concrete object if it begins to express and thus expresses some tushurieti, to a proper noun turns and remains. Big jar words do not individualize, concretize, that is, any object

If it does not express, the related noun, which indicates the forms of negative relief, is an appellative will remain. Thus, toponyms are the concretization of the geographical concept and emerged from related nouns in the process of individualization will be Toponymization is usually the first general concept of a specific object occurs during the connection process. Therefore, a single word or a combination of words at the same time, it must be a related noun (if the concept is a concrete object if it does not represent) or it can be a toponym (if it represents a geographical object). For example, a wheat field is any field planted with wheat, and a wheat field is a concrete one like the name of a place. From the moment geographical names separated from the lexicon of related nouns moves away from the features of the geographical object it represents. Toponyms rather than emphasizing the different features of this object in the speech. It helps to distinguish a concrete object from others. To Toponym the transformed word acquires a new meaning, now this word is concrete, unique, a new one becomes a concept.

Geographical names often come from a concept that represents a geographic object it has another meaning. For example, Karakishloq means a smaller population point is understood. Everyone is wondering whether the village will

be black does not appear. The name of this village comes from the name of the black clan only an ethnographer who knows the Uzbek clans down to the smallest branches has come out can tell. Or many on why Wednesday Village is so called He doesn't think about where he is, which region, which district, which village is more important. Here you may remember the notion that Wednesday was the market.

A word that has become a toponym is often a typical toponym with the discovery of a new meaning takes shape, additions (suffixes) typical for toponyms appear. Toponyms of Uzbekistan, in particular - istan (Shuristan, 3Agistan), -iya (Uzbekiya, Affixes such as Mingiya), -kor {Pakhtakor, Lalmikor), - cha (Kudukcha, Bulogcha) is characteristic. Currently, the degree of toponymization of geographical areas is different. Some one in toponyms, the meaning of words before they become toponyms is clearly known, partially preserved in other toponyms, the third is known in the same names it is felt unknown, and in others it is completely lost. That's why it is correct to change the toponyms, the meaning of which is unclear, to make them understandable no, such names are valuable linguistic and historical remnants of ancient languages may be memos.

Geographical names are the product of people's creativity. Mostly toponyms does not arise from delusion. Historical geographical objects, for example, a village may be called differently. Let's say, relief, water source, contribute to its development depending on the names of the people who added it, –so-and-so village||, “so-and-so village” can be treated as Eventually one of these names will win out.

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